

Integrating the Geographic Dimension into Information-Epidemic Co-evolution: A Spatially Explicit Agent-Based Model

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With virtual and physical spaces intertwined by advancing information technology, understanding information–epidemic co-evolution is crucial for improving epidemic control. Researchers often use microscopic Markov chains in multilayer networks to study information–epidemic co-evolution. However, those models neglect the geographical perspective, constrained by two main issues: 1) Spatial Representation Deficiency: They rely on abstract networks that omit the critical geographic dimension necessary for realistically depicting information–epidemic interactions; 2) Network Linkage Deficiency: They overlook that individuals who have physical contact are highly likely to form virtual social links—indicating that these two network layers are not independent. To address this, we propose the Agent-based Spatially Explicit Info-Epidemic Model (ASEI) incorporating geographic space into information–epidemic dynamics. First, ASEI remedies the spatial representation deficiency by constructing spatially explicit multilayer networks, embedding interactions within realistic geographic contexts in households, workplaces, schools, and communities at a city scale. Second, drawing on a questionnaire-based study, we demonstrate and model the reciprocal influence between physical interactions and virtual links. Building on these findings, we then establish a spatially explicit information–epidemic network that integrates the network structures of both physical and virtual interactions. Finally, we employ an agent-based simulation at the city scale to capture individual interactions across these spatial layers, modeling the spatiotemporal co-evolution of information–epidemic.

Our simulation results reveal:

1. Information dissemination exhibits distinct spatial clustering patterns in its early stages, further reinforced as the epidemic unfolds.
2. This interdependent network significantly amplifies the influence of information on epidemic spread, demonstrating its far-reaching real-world impact.
3. Targeted information dissemination within specific urban geographic communities validates the model's utility for spatially targeted control strategies.

Overall, ASEI is capable of offering new insights into information–epidemic co-evolution, emphasizing geography's critical role in network interactions and guiding effective control strategies for urban environments.

Keywords: Information–epidemic co-evolution; Geographic dimension; Agent-based modeling; ; Urban environment ; Network interdependence